

EXPERIMENTAL AND DESIGN FEASIBILITY STUDY OF BOLTED JOINTS STRENGTH OF COMPOSITE PLATES

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ABSTRACT

The results of bolted joints tests of some composite materials are considered under influence of tighten moment and design parameters. It is shown the opportunity of the local strength calculation. The design reinforcement of fasteners zone questions are discussed.

Keywords: composite materials, bolt joints, strength.

The operation practice of laminated composite products shows, that their joints are not so well studied as joints of isotropical materials and require a special research with estimation as the local and as the general joints strength.

1. CALCULATION ANALYSIS OF LOCAL STRENGTH

The three-measure analysis of stress distribution in fastener bolt hole region in anisotropical plate connects with great difficulties due to contact form problem. All calculation methods base on the continuous medium mechanics, but it is rather conventionally for composite materials in stress concentration zone. The theoretical stress concentration expression in fastener bolt zone was shown in [1], and three-measure finite elements were used in our work [2] for modeling the fastener bolt region. It was suggested [1,2] to use various forms of strength criterious for different composite materials. This analysis for fibreglass and carbon-plastics bolted joints showed the local break-down of composite materials for service tighten moments and rather small loads. Results are in good agreement with [3], where the destroy process in hole zone was investigated. It is necessary to mark that local strength, which mainly depends of the polymer matrix strength, does not reach the joint's strength limit.

2. EXPERIMENTAL BOLT JOINTS MODELS INVESTIGATION

Some mechanical methods are used for affording composite materials bolt joints (washeres, gaskets, tighten moments and so on), all this methods call for special experimental study. Most polymeric composite materials have the little crush strength. Mechanical properties of contrast composite materials carbon, aramid (organic) and layer metal-plastics were tested in special fixture, which allowed by bolt hole size variation with constant values of e, l, w and with values of tighten moments 0, 10, 20, 40 Nm to estimate design parameters $w/d, e/d, h$ (fig-1). For one experimental point 8-10 tests were studied. The statistics procedure with tests results was done. Experimental data are represented by the normal value distribution. Variation coefficients were less than 15 percent during testing.

Fig-1. Testing fixture - a ; specimen - b.

Aramid (organic) plastic consisted from fabric and fiber CBM in one to one relation with ЭДТ-10 binder, moulded by 85 KPa pressure in vacuum and 180°C during 6 hours.

Carbon КМУ-4А plastic consisted from laminates of tape АУ-П-0,2 with ЭНФБ binder, moulded by 490 KPa and 160°C temperature during 6 hours. The laminates plastic placement was $[90/0_3+45/0_3/90]_S$.

Three-, five- and seven-layers metal-aramid consisted of aluminium layers of Д164АТ with 0,5 mm thickness and stressed aramid fabric 56313 laminates with BK-41 binder.

On the fig.2 showed part of test results in form of strength surfaces (nominal values of crush stresses $\sigma_c = P/dh$, where P is the joint destroy load). The tests cutting angle θ° indicated from one direction laminates and in metal-aramid plastic from the direction of metal rolled. Tests has rectangular form, length $l=150$ mm, width $w=30$ and 40 mm, $e=18$ and 20 mm for carbon, aramid and metal-aramid correspondently.

Fig.2. Strength surfaces: ten-laminates carbon - a ; influence of angle cutting in carbon with 20 Nm tighten moment - b ; ten-laminates aramid - c ; metal-aramid with 10 Nm tighten moment.

The destroy form of all tests depended of as tests cutting and as tighten moment values. The effect of test thickness (in range 1-5 mm) considerably was shown for thin carbon plastic (1 mm tests), The most strength showed tests with cutting angle value $\theta^{\circ} = \pm 45^{\circ}$ when percent content of $\pm 45^{\circ}$ laminates is about 80. The strength decreased during difference cutting tests angles from 0° till 90° for tests with more then 2 mm thickness. The best crush strength because of its design showed the metal-aramid plastic. Using fasteners of less size is more rational for it. For all composite materials the preliminar joint tightening showed the considerably strength increasing due to design reinforcement plastics.

Obtained graphical strength surfaces may be used for choosing rationally design parameters, moments tightening and checking the joints strength reserve.

3. THE DESIGN REINFORCEMENT OF JOINTS

The tendency of the best using of composite materials due to reinforcement design of joints is main now. For example of such designing let us consider results by Necrasov's work [4], where joints of metal and carbon plates with metall applied plate were investigated (fig.3a). This design is more rational from the view of technology and strength, than the different methods of reinforcement of composite materials in bolted hole zone by various space metal layers.

The experimental investigation showed that such joint design increased the joint strength till the composite material plate strength.

The tests showed so that the joints strength with strong tighten moment decreased unconsiderably because of the stress relaxation after keeping in air and in water during about service period. The same effect investigations showed after keeping joints in high temperature ($120 - 150^{\circ}\text{C}$) during 60-80 min.

The fatigue strength tests (fig.3b) with tension cycle load (velocity of load 5 mm/min) showed good serviceability of this joints on base of 10 cycles with load level 0,95;0,90;0,85 ... from break-down load. The growth curves on fig.3 note fatigue curves for two values of tighten moment (15 and 40 Nm) and crack growth curves - the low significant boundary (95 percent unfailure probability). Part of tests beard more than base number cycles.

The training of joints during tests resulted to increasing their strength and longevity.

Fig.3. The joint design - a; fatigue tests results - b.

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